

Figure S2.1. Response plots for combined model

Figure S2.2. Response plots for hibernacula model

Table S2.3. Response plots for maternity models

Table S2.4. Response plots for transition model

Figure S2.5. Response plot for ecoregion 1

Figure S2.6. Response plots for ecoregion 4

bio03

bio12

bio15

bio18

DEM

slope

Table S2.7 Response plots for ecoregion 5

Figure S2.8. Response plots for ecoregion 6

Figure S2.9. Response plots for ecoregion 8

bio03

bio12

bio15

bio18

DEM

slope

Figure S2.10. Response plots for ecoregion 13

bio03

bio12

bio15

bio18

DEM

slope

Figure S2.11. Response plots for ecoregion 14

bio03

bio12

bio15

bio18

DEM

slope

Figure S2.12. Response plots for ecoregion 78

bio03

bio12

bio15

bio18

DEM

slope

Figure S2.13. Response plots for ecoregion 85

bio03

bio12

bio15

bio18

DEM

slope